

PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PRESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN

Muminov Obidkhon Norkhujajevich

Director of the Presidential School in Fergana, independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8364128>

Abstract. *This article deals with pedagogical strategies for improving the quality of education in the Presidential schools and their impact on the educational process of students, consistent monitoring and management of the educational process in the Presidential schools.*

Keywords: *era of globalization, international education standards, patriotism, Agency for Specialized Educational Institutions, monitoring*

We all know that today the era of globalization is developing rapidly around the world, and this, in turn, is being considered by our government as the most important issue of the agenda of developing competitive personnel. After all, the ideas and teachings of scholars such as Bukhari and Termizi, Farabi and Ferghani, Ibn Sina and Al-Khwarizmi, Ulugbek and Navoi, who were born and raised in the territory of our country on the basis of the specific values of our culture formed in our republic, universal human principles, scientific and theoretical aimed at the spiritual upliftment of young people. views and the fact that our country has passed a new stage of development and its contributions to the entire world civilization are incomparable. As a proof of this, the research of this scientific and cultural heritage, scientific research, in turn, is reflected in the works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

The development of the new Uzbek society is directly related to its material and spiritual spheres. Due to the global changes in the whole world and in our country, overcoming the crisis situations in social life, economy, ecology, demography, and building a new type of society in which the existing negative situations of modern life will be eliminated requires the cooperation of the state and citizens. At the same time, the results of fundamental reforms in educational processes were widely seen at the meeting of the honorable President on August 28, 2023 regarding "Priority tasks for further improving the quality of education in schools, increasing the number of students and improving the qualifications of teachers and creating suitable conditions for them". was discussed in lam, and this, in turn, we can interpret as an important example of the attention paid by the head of state to education.

As a result of public discussion, the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, which consists of the following seven priority areas, developed based on the principles of "From Action Strategy to Development Strategy", was approved: These strategies include the following 7 directions: *Direction 1:* "Human building a people-friendly state by increasing its value and further developing a free civil society".

Direction 2: "Turning the principles of justice and the rule of law into the most basic and necessary conditions for development in our country."

Direction 3: "Rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates."

Direction 4: "Effective social policy, development of human capital."

Direction 5: "Ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to new levels."

Direction 6: "Addressing universal problems based on national interests."

Direction 7: "Strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open pragmatic and active foreign policy."

Love for the motherland, patriotic feelings are not feelings which arise and form in a person by themselves, unconsciously. Those feelings are formed and developed in each person under the influence of the social and cultural environment that surrounds him in the society, based on the education and upbringing of the society. Of course, these qualities are perfected in young people through their activities as individuals. Based on these, we can say that only the formation of a legal state ensures the high importance of law. At this point, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 526 of June 25, 2019, it was also defined in the Regulation on Presidential schools. On the basis of this regulation, the following goals and main tasks of the Presidential schools were determined, and this also reflected aspects such as the establishment of the Presidential schools and the setting of priority tasks.

Figure 1. The main goals and objectives of the Presidential school

Below, we considered it permissible to get acquainted with the organizational structure, rights and obligations of the Presidential schools, which were established in 2019 and are currently operating in the territory of 14 regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

- admission of students within the set annual quota (divided into two classes - 12 students, 24 students);
- development and approval of the training schedule based on the approved training plans and programs;
- participation in meetings, assemblies and other events dedicated to the discussion of important issues in the field of state policy, socio-cultural and public education and solving urgent problems by the Ministry and other state bodies and organizations;
- cooperation with the relevant structural units of the Ministry in order to fulfill the assigned tasks in a timely, efficient and high-quality manner;
- handing out the graduates of the Presidential schools the relevant international program diplomas (International Baccalaureate, Advanced Placement or International Advanced Levels)

that give them the opportunity to study in leading foreign higher education institutions, along with a state model educational document (certificate, certificate);

- concluding a contract with business entities based on the best offers by conducting a selection process for organizing hygienic healthy meals.

- Presidential schools, as well as other legal documents, to perform tasks and functions specified in their charter in a timely, qualitative and effective manner;

- quality and efficient organization of the educational process;

- to ensure compliance with the rights and legal interests of students, teachers and other employees of presidential schools;

- is obliged to ensure that the forms, methods and means of organizing the educational process comply with the state educational standards of general secondary education.

Organization of educational process in presidential schools is carried out in the following order:

- The educational process in presidential schools is carried out in accordance with the curricula and programs developed in cooperation with specialized foreign organizations providing services in the field of general secondary education and approved by the Ministry, taking into account the state educational standards of general secondary education. In this, there is a department for working with Presidential schools under the Agency of Specialized Educational Institutions, and this department operates as the main management and monitoring organizational structure of 14 schools.

- The schedule of the educational process, the types and duration of educational activities, the educational load of students, the forms of organization and other issues of the educational process are developed together with specialized foreign organizations providing services in the field of education and are approved by the Ministry in accordance with the educational programs and other normative legal documents of the Ministry is determined.

Quality control of education is carried out in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards of general secondary education, taking into account international educational standards. Special foreign organizations may also be involved to ensure quality control of education. Graduates of presidential schools are issued with a state model educational document (certificate, certificate) and this certificate can be downloaded electronically from the erp.uz database. Graduates of the 11th grade of presidential schools have the right to pass international qualification exams (International Baccalaureate, Advanced Placement or International Advanced Levels) based on selected subjects, and upon successful completion, they receive an international diploma that provides access to leading foreign higher education institutions. , giving information about the A-Level exam:

The A-level certificate offered by the Cambridge Assessment International Education organization is an international higher standard certificate, with A+(a+), A(a), B(b), C(c), D(d) or E(e) in exams. degrees can be obtained. - A+(a+) is the highest and E(e) is the lowest indicator. In order to obtain an A-level certificate, not only the students of the Presidential School, but also all those who wish to take these exams. Conditions for this have been established in 14 Presidential schools. The A-Level certificate is recognized in more than 1,750 universities in 95 countries (including the TOP 20 by the Times Higher Education organization, as well as in Great Britain). Exams are traditionally held twice a year - in October-November and May-June. Candidates can register for autumn exams in August-September, and for May-June exams in January-February.

Cambridge Assessment offers more than 50 types of subjects for the exam, and the candidate chooses 3 to 5 subjects. In addition to A-levels, Cambridge Assessment also awards AS and IGCSE certificates. Pupils of presidential schools:

- IGCSE exam — in the 8th-9th grade,
- AS exam - in 10th grade,
- A-level is passed in the 11th grade.

Figure 3. Lesson process in Presidential schools.

Applicants from abroad (who are not students of Presidential schools) can take any type of exam, depending on their knowledge and desire, regardless of the grade they study in.

In conclusion, it can be said that our government has developed enough decisions and instructions on the establishment and development of the above 14 Presidential schools, in which the principals of these schools must have the required level of knowledge, management and managerial skills, as well as justice and transparency, a responsible approach is required. Of course, in the direction of this noble goal, we will all have to carry out relevant work with patriotic feelings and high responsibility for the development of New Uzbekistan, because in the words of our President, "New Uzbekistan starts from the school threshold."

REFERENCES

1. Collections of selected works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev-2019 year
2. On the Strategy of Actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947. February 7, 2017.

3. Video selector meeting of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev on "Priority tasks for further improving the quality of education in schools, increasing the number of students and improving the qualifications of teachers and creating suitable conditions for them". August 28, 2023
4. A Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on approval of the statute on Presidential schools. June 25, 2019, No. 526
5. Abdullaeva B.S. Methodological and didactic foundations of interdisciplinarity (in the example of teaching mathematics in academic lyceums in social and humanitarian directions): *Ped. science. Ph.D. Diss. abstract.* - T., 2006, -52 p
6. Muminov O, N -Prezident maktablarida ta'lim sifatini oshirishning pedagogik strategiyalari , *Toshkent Davlat Pedagogika Universiteti Ilmiy Axborotlari Ilmiy-Nazariy Jurnali*, ISSN 2181-9580 , 2023 yil 8-son, 355-362 b
7. Muminov O, N- Prezident maktablarida o'quv-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etishning pedagogik-didaktik va normativ asoslari, *Toshkent Davlat Pedagogika Universiteti Ilmiy Axborotlari Ilmiy-Nazariy Jurnali*, ISSN 2181-9580 , 2023 yil 9-son, 102-108 b.
8. Muminov O, -Increasing tourist attraction to Uzbekistan in digital economy period by enhancing service quality, 2023/8/1, *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability (EJRDS)*, Volume-4, ISSN: 2660-55, pages 13-15, editor <https://www.scholarzest.com>
9. Muminov O,- Development of hospitality industry by improving service quality and customer satisfaction in Uzbekistan,2021, ISBN: 978-93-96573-28-3 Published by Novateur Publication 466, Sadashiv Peth, M.S.India-411030 <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aOilsJQAAAAAJ&hl=ru>
10. Obidkhon, Norkhujayevich Muminov- ВЛИЯНИЕ НА УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬЮ , 2021/11 , *Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning muammolari va istiqbollari* , Том 1, Номер 2 , Страницы 53-63, О'ZBEKISTON JURNALISTIKA VA OMMAVIY KOMMUNIKATSIYALAR UNIVERSITETI
11. Obidkhon, Norkhujayevich Muminov, Muxridin Nasridinov Vaslidin o'g'li - Comparative Typology of Verbal Means Expressing the Concept of
12. "Goal" in Languages with Different Systems , *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE* Volume: 02 Issue: 12 December 2021